

Synthesis of some Oxazolo-, Imidazolo-, Selenadiazolo-, Thiadiazolo-, Azetidino- and Thiazolidinono-8-hydroxyquinolines

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Some new ϵ (7)-oxazolo- and/or imidazolo-8-hydroxyquinoline (4a-f) were prepared through the reaction of 5(7) formyl-8-hydroxyquinolines (1, 2) with *o*-aminophenol, 1-amino-2-naphthol and *o*-phenylenediamine by fusion in presence of piperidine as a catalyst. Also, 5-selenadiazolo-, thiadiazolo-, azetidino- and thiazolidinono-8-hydroxyquinolines (6, 7, 9a-c, 10a-c) were prepared by the reaction of 5-acetylsemicarbazone-8-hydroxyquinoline (4) and the Schiff bases (8a-c) with selenium dioxide, thionyl chloride, chloroacetyl chloride and thioglycolic acid, respectively.

It was reported that oxazolo- and imidazolo-quinolines are potent as bactericides¹⁻⁷. Also, 1,2,3-selena- and thia-diazole have found medicinal application as bactericides⁸⁻¹¹, virucides⁹, fungicides¹², herbicides^{13, 14}, allergy inhibitors¹⁵, sedatives and tranquilisers¹⁶. In view of this and in extension to our work¹⁷, some new oxazolo-, imidazolo-, selenadiazolo-, thiadiazolo-, azetidino- and thiazolidinono-quinolines were synthesised.

Results and Discussion

5(7)-(2-Benzoxazolo-, 2-naphth[1,2-*d*]oxazolo-, and 2-benzimidazolo)-8-hydroxyquinolines were prepared by fusion of 5(7)-formyl-8-hydroxyquinoline (1, 2) with equivalent amounts of *o*-aminophenol, 1-amino-2-naphthol and *o*-phenylenediamine, respectively. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis and by ir spectra which showed well defined bands characterising the oxazole ring at 1 580 (C=N), 1 050-1 730 (C-O-C cyclic)¹⁸ and 3 200 cm⁻¹ (NH of imidazole) with the lack of NH₂ band.

The hitherto unreported selena- and thiazolidin heterocycles (6, 7) incorporating 8-hydroxyquinoline moiety were synthesised. The key intermediate of such compounds was 5-acetyl-8-hydroxyquinoline semicarbazone (5) obtained by dissolving 5-acetyl-8-hydroxyquinoline in pyridine followed by addition of the calculated amount of semicarbazide hydrochloride. The semicarbazone (5) was oxidised by selenium dioxide in glacial acetic acid to give 5-(1,2,3-selenadiazolo)-8-hydroxyquinoline (6). When the semicarbazone was allowed to react with thionyl chloride, 5-(1,2,3-thiadiazolo)-8-hydroxyquinoline (7) was obtained^{19, 20}. The structures of these compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and nmr

spectral data. The ir spectra showed bands at 1 580 (C=N), 3 300-3 200 (NH₂) and 1 710 cm⁻¹ (sec amide) for the semicarbazone, at 850-800 (C-Se-N), 1 370-1 330 (C-N) and 950 cm⁻¹ (in plane deformation for ring breathing) for selenadiazole, at 770-700 (C-S), 1 315 (C-N), 1 190 cm⁻¹ (C-H, in-plane deformation), and at 900 cm⁻¹ (ring breathing) for thiadiazole. The nmr spectra (CDCl₃) showed a singlet at δ 9.4 (1H of selenadiazole ring), a multiplet at δ 8.1-7 (6H, Ar) for selenadiazole, a singlet at δ 8.8 (1H of thiadiazole ring), and a multiplet at δ 8.2-7.3 (6H, Ar) for the thiadiazole.

1-(*p*-Substituted-phenyl)-3-chloro-4-methyl-4-(8-chloroacetyloxyquinolin-5-yl)-2-azetidione (9a-c) and 2-(2-methyl-2-(8-hydroxyquinolin-5-yl)-3-substituted-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone were prepared via cyclocondensation reaction between the Schiff bases (obtained by refluxing of 5-acetyl-8-hydroxyquinoline with aromatic amines in absolute ethanol and piperidine as a catalyst) and chloroacetyl chloride or thioglycolic acid, respectively. The ir spectra showed characteristic bands for azetidione at 1 730 cm⁻¹ and for thiazolidinone at 1 700-1 650 cm⁻¹.

Antimicrobial activity: 5-Acetyl-8-hydroxyquinoline (3) is quite potent against the tested fungi *Penicillium not.*, *Aspergillus fla.* and *Stachybotrys atra.*, less potent against the tested bacteria *Bacillus sub.*, *Micrococcus let.* and *Serratia sp.* Replacement of the 5-acetyl groups by 5-azolyl moieties benzoxazolyl, naphth[1,2-*d*]oxazolyl, and benzimidazolyl, destroy this activity while the 5-thiadiazole (7) is potent only against *Stachybotrys atra*. Replacement of the hetero-sulphur atom in thiadiazole by selenium atom in selenadiazole (6) inhibit its activity. Schiff's base derivative of 3 has no fungicidal effect except against *Stachybotrys*

1

2

5

8a-c

 a ; R = H, b ; OCH₃, c ; Cl

4

3

6

9a-c

7

10a-c

- a ; R₁ = 2-benzoxazolyl, R₂ = H
 b ; R₁ = H ; R₂ = 2-benzoxazolyl
 c ; R₁ = 2-naphth[1,2-d]oxazolyl, R₂ = H
 d ; R₁ = H, R₂ = 2-naphth[1,2-d]oxazolyl
 e ; R₁ = 2-benzimidazolyl, R₂ = H
 f ; R₁ = H, R₂ = 2-benzimidazolyl

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.	Colour	Yield %	M.p. °C	Molecular formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
					N	S	Cl
4a	Brown	63	242-4	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	10.73 (10.69)	—	—
4b	Pale brown	50	345-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	10.67 (10.69)	—	—
4c	Brown	56	340-2	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	9.10 (8.97)	—	—
4d	Brown	57	335-7	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂	8.89 (8.97)	—	—
4e	Dark brown	53	225-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂	16.13 (16.09)	—	—
4f	Yellow	40	265-7	C ₁₆ H ₁₁ ON ₂	15.92 (16.09)	—	—
8a	Pale yellow	70	145	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ ON ₂	10.73 (10.69)	—	—
8b	Yellow	66	126-8	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂	9.67 (9.59)	—	—
8c	Pale yellow	60	130	C ₁₇ H ₁₀ ON ₂ Cl	9.50 (9.44)	—	12.01 (11.97)
9a	Pale yellow	30	174-6	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.69 (6.75)	—	17.20 (17.11)
9b	Brown	30	188-90	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.33 (6.29)	—	16.13 (15.96)
9c	Yellow	27	154	C ₂₁ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂ Cl ₂	6.16 (6.23)	—	23.77 (23.69)
10a	Pale yellow	33	160-2	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ S	8.40 (8.33)	9.47 (9.52)	—
10b	Pale yellow	28	176-8	C ₂₀ H ₁₄ O ₂ N ₂ S	7.71 (7.65)	8.92 (8.74)	—
10c	Pale yellow	30	213-5	C ₁₆ H ₁₀ O ₂ N ₂ SCl	—	9.63 (9.98)	8.99 (8.64)

TABLE 2—ANTIMICROBIAL ACTIVITY OF SELECTED COMPOUNDS

Compd. no.,	Inhibition zone (mm)								
	<i>P. not.</i> (100 ppm)	<i>A. flav.</i> (100 ppm)	100	<i>S. atra.</i>			<i>B. sub.</i>	<i>M. lut.</i>	<i>S. sp.</i>
3	30	35	71	55	25	12.5	22	19	23
7	—	—	30	—	—	—	—	—	—
8b	—	—	40	—	—	—	—	—	19

atra. (4 cm inhibition zone, 100 ppm). Cyclo-addition products of the Schiff bases either as β lactams (9a–c) or thiazolidinones (10a–c) destroy this activity (Table 2).

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The ir spectra were determined with a Perkin-Elmer 599B spectrophotometer using KBr disc. Nmr spectra were carried out in CDCl_3 using a Varian EM 390 (90 MHz) spectrometer.

5(7)-[2-Benzoxazolo-, 2-naphth-[1,2-d]oxazolo- and 2-benzimidazo-]-8-hydroxyquinolines (4a–c): Equimolar amounts (0.003) mol of 5(7)-formyl-8-hydroxyquinolines (1, 2) and the selected aromatic amines (*o*-aminophenol, 1-amino-2-naphthol and *o*-phenylenediamine) were fused together for 2 min using piperidine (2 drops) as a catalyst. The products were extracted with absolute ethanol (15 ml), concentrated, cooled, filtered off and air-dried (Table 1).

5-Acetylsemicarbazone-8 hydroxyquinoline (5): To a solution of 5-acetyl-8-hydroxyquinoline (0.9 g, 0.005 mol) in pyridine (10 ml) was added with shaking a solution of semicarbazide hydrochloride (1.2 g, 0.01 mol) in water (1.2 ml) for 15 min. The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 24h. The precipitated solid was filtered off, washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol to yield the product in the form of yellow crystals (1.1g, 92%), m.p. 258–60° (Found: N, 23.01. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2\text{N}_4$ calcd. for: N, 22.95%), R_f 0.62 (benzene-ethanol, 2:1).

5-(1,2,3-Selenadiazolo)-8-hydroxyquinoline (6): To a solution of 5-acetylsemicarbazone-8-hydroxyquinoline (1 g, 0.004 mol) in boiled acetic acid (30 ml) was added portionwise finely powdered selenium dioxide (0.009 mol). The reaction mixture was heated on a water-bath with stirring for 1 h and filtered while hot over ice. The precipitated product was extracted with chloroform and the organic layer washed successively with water, 10% sodium hydrogen carbonate and finally with water. The chloroform layer was dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated under vacuum. The remaining residue was recrystallised from acetic acid to yield the title compound in the form of brown crystals (0.7 g, 64%), m.p. 340° (Found: C, 47.91; H, 2.61; N, 15.16. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{ON}_3\text{Se}$ calcd. for: C, 47.83; H, 2.54; N, 15.22%), R_f 0.58 (toluene-methanol, 3:1).

5-(1,2,3-Thiadiazolo)-8-hydroxyquinoline (7): 5-Acetylsemicarbazone-8-hydroxyquinoline (1g, 0.004 mol) was added portionwise to cooled thionyl chloride solution (15 ml). The reaction mixture was left at room temperature for 2 h and excess of thionyl chloride removed under vacuum. The residue was triturated with cold saturated sodium carbonate solution and the product extracted from chloroform. The chloroform layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The product was recrystallised from ethanol to give green crystals (0.6 g, 67%), m.p. 158–60° (Found: N, 18.29; S, 14.05. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_7\text{ON}_3\text{S}$ calcd. for: N, 18.34; S, 13.97%), R_f 0.51 (benzene-ethanol, 3:2).

Reaction of 5-acetyl-8-hydroxyquinoline with *p*-substituted aniline. Synthesis of Schiff bases (7a–c): A mixture of 5-acetyl-8-hydroxyquinoline (3.7 g, 0.02 mol) and aniline, *p*-anisidine or *p*-chloroaniline (0.02 mol) was heated, under reflux in absolute ethanol (50 ml) containing piperidine (1 ml) for 10 h. The reaction mixture was filtered while hot and the filtrate evaporated to half its volume, whereby crystalline solids were separated (Table 1).

1-Substituted-phenyl-3-chloro-4-methyl-4-(8-chloroacetoxyquinolin-5-yl)-2-azetidinone (9a–c):

To a solution of the Schiff base (8a–c; 0.002 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml) containing triethylamine (0.004 mol) was added dropwise at room temperature of chloroacetyl chloride (0.004 mol). The reaction mixture was shaken electrically for 6 h and then kept at room temperature for a further 36 h. The precipitated triethylamine hydrochloride was filtered off and the filtrate evaporated to dryness under vacuum. The precipitated product was crystallised from benzene (Table 1).

2-(2-Methyl-2-(8-hydroxyquinoline-5-yl)-2-substituted-phenyl-4-thiazolidinone (10a–c):

A mixture of the Schiff base (8a–c; 0.002 mol) in dry benzene (10 ml) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.002 mol) was heated under reflux for 12 h. The solvent benzene was evaporated and the solid product thiazolidinone was washed repeatedly with a 1:1 mixture of benzene-petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°). The product was recrystallised from benzene (Table 1).

Antimicrobial activity: Biological activity of selected new synthesised compounds were tested.

Thus, compounds 1-10 were dissolved in ethylene glycol (10 mg/100 ml, 100 ppm) and transferred to filter paper disc (15 mm) and determined by diffusion-plate method²¹. The antifungal activity was determined against *Penicillium notatum*, *Aspergillus flavus* and *Stachybotrys atra*. The antibacterial effect of the same compounds was determined against *Bacillus subtilis*, *Micrococcus lutes* and *Serratia sp.*

Bacterial suspension was prepared by adding sterile distilled water (10 ml) to a 10-day old culture of the test bacteria grown on a nutrient agar of NA²². The culture consisted of beef extract (10 g dm⁻³), peptone (10 g dm⁻³), sodium chloride (5 g dm⁻³) and agar (10 g dm⁻³) at pH 7.4. Aliquots (1 ml) of the bacterial suspension were added to NA petridishes (one plate/test compound). The excess liquid has removed and filter paper disc (15 mm dia) containing the test compound was placed on the plate. Plates were then incubated at 37° and the diameter of the inhibition zones measured after 24 h. These experiments were repeated thrice.

Spore suspension was prepared²³ by adding sterile distilled water (10 ml) to a 10-day old culture of the test fungus grown on potato dextrose-agar (PDA) potatose (peeled and sliced, 200 g dm⁻³), dextrose (20 g dm⁻³), agar (17 g dm⁻³) at pH 6.5. Aliquots (1 ml) of the spore suspension were added to PDA petridishes (plate/test compound). The excess liquids was removed and filter paper disc incubated at 37°, and the inhibition zone measured after 3 days. The experiments were carried out in triplicate.

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